

Swedish registry data at ASC

Swedish national registry data division Ageing and Social Change (ASC) includes several registers compiled into one database by Statistics Sweden (SCB) on behalf of Linköping University on the basis of ethical approval (Dnr 201629331). The database includes information from several registers, such as the Swedish register of the total population, the Swedish register of education, the job-register and the health insurance and labour market studies.

The database includes all people born in 1968 or earlier that has been registered in Sweden at any time between 1990-2018 and their registered partners. The total number of individuals is 7,131,235. For this population, the database covers information from all years between 1990 and 2018, regardless of age. The dataset includes various levels which are individual, firm, workplace, municipality, and region.

The individual level information includes their demographic and socioeconomic characteristics such as birth date, place, having a foreign parent, socioeconomic characteristics such as income, education, occupation as well as housing, partner, and migration histories of individuals.

The firm and workplace information include the place, sector of the organization, the employee composition of the organization such as the share of the males and females in different education levels and the total salaries paid.

Municipality information includes the number of inhabitants, population composition such as number of individuals in higher education or seeking a job, income and sector structure of the population.

The data cannot be made publicly available as its use is restricted by the Data use agreement between Statistics Sweden and Linköping University, especially by the “Sekretessöverenskommelse mellan Statistiska centralbyran (SCB) och Linköpings universitet”, both signed on April 20, 2017. Interested parties may apply for data use at Statistics Sweden, who will process the request according to their regulations in line with Swedish legislation.